

HISTORICAL FOUNDATIONS AND THEORETICAL-CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS OF SOCIAL POLICY

Xazratkulov Sherzod Abror o'g'li
Uzbekistan State World Languages University
PhD student of the Department of Social Sciences,
E-mail: sherzodovvv@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7162397>

Annotation: The thesis substantiates social policy of Islam Karimov who was the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Islam Karimov, as the founder of independence and new statehood of our country, great politician and wise reformer, who took care of people's welfare, who made a significant contribution to ensuring peace and stability in the region and the world, won great respect among our people and the world community. The noble qualities inherent in the First President of our country, such as unwavering will, patriotism, courage, justice, sincerity and sensitivity, have become a vivid example for all of us. Islam Karimov put interests of Uzbekistan above all else and spared no effort in the name of its development.

Keywords: Uzbek model, the Scientific and Enlightenment Memorial Complex, social policies.

INTRODUCTION

The comprehensive measures being implemented in our country for the consistent renewal of all

spheres of society and accelerated reform of public relations are primarily aimed at improving the living standards of our compatriots, ensuring the interests of the population in need of social protection, further development and prosperity of our homeland. The strengthening of social policies is becoming increasingly important against a backdrop of growing global tensions. Strong social policy is one of the principles developed by the First President Islam Karimov "Uzbek model" of development, the concept of building a new state and society, fully justified in practice. Its essence lies in the constant attention of the state and society to the targeted protection of all segments of the population, especially the socially needy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In accordance with the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev №DP-2744 dated January 25, 2017 «On perpetuating the memory of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Abdughanievich Karimov» and №DP-2929 dated April 25, 2017 «On the

organization of the activity of the Scientific and Enlightenment Memorial Complex named after the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov at the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan» in the country consistently implements the memory of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, his enormous contribution to the achievement of independence and the building of national statehood, the historical role of Islam Karimov's personality, and to the representation of the general public, especially the youth, and foreign guests with the history of the formation and strengthening of Uzbekistan as an independent state under the leadership of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and education of the younger generation on the example of life and activity of Islam Karimov, in the spirit of history and political culture, patriotism and responsibility for the fate of the Motherland.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since its first years of independence, Uzbekistan has abandoned "shock therapy" and has been implementing gradual reforms. The principles of development also determined the priority of the economy over politics, the rule of law and a strong social policy.

Formed the mechanism of strengthening of the social sector, guaranteeing targeted and efficient social protection. Institutional bases of social support of the population have been created. In 1991, the law «On social protection of disabled persons in the Republic of Uzbekistan» was adopted. In addition, laws "On state pension provision of citizens", "on employment", "on protection of citizens 'health" and other legislative acts are being implemented. Their consistent implementation, the annual allocation of about 60 percent of the State budget in the social sphere contribute to the preservation of social stability in the country, strengthening the faith of people in the future. Along with the reforms implemented in the most important sectors of the economy, market reforms are taking place in health care, education, culture and art, physical culture and sports. Uzbekistan was the first country in the Commonwealth to develop and implement an absolutely new and effective model of education on the basis of a National training programme. It is remembered that in even the most difficult period's special attention was paid to youth policy. The law "On the foundations of the state youth policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan", adopted on November 20, 1991, is one of the first laws of our independent Republic. It has become a vivid expression of the attitude towards the younger generation as the most important asset and significant platform for creating the necessary conditions for its harmonious development.

In accordance with the law "on education" and the National program for training,

the country has established a system to provide modern specialists in the rapidly developing sectors of the economy and social sphere. Modern schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges have been built in the most remote villages.

CONCLUSION

Today, our country is gaining high marks from the world's leading reputable rating agencies for economic growth, creating the best conditions for doing business, ensuring security in the country, caring for the health of citizens, which is a clear example of the implementation of a deeply thought-out far-sighted and wise policy of the state.

References:

1. K. Komilov, O'. Khasanboev, N. Hoshimov. Religious extremism and international terrorism are a threat to the development of society. - T.: Tashkent Islamic University publishing house, 2019.
2. Turdiyev Bekhruz Sobirovich, Spiritual renewal: new decisions and strategies of viable reforms // Scientific Information of Bukhara State University. -2018.
3. Safoev S. Geopolitics in Central Asia, - T .: 2015, p. 41
4. Khujanova T. Problems of perfect protection of the young generation in globalization processes //Science and practice: a new level of integration in the modern world. - 2019. - p. 15-18.